

Mukhabarah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics surrounding Mukhabarah agreements on Islamic Financial Inclusion using a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Mukhabarah " within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around Mukhabarah contracts based on the journals that have been collected. The results of the research show that there are 6 research topics surrounding Mukhabarah contracts, including the differences between Mukhabarah and Muzara'ah contracts, the application of Mukhabarah contracts in the agricultural sector, in salt ponds, in maro profit sharing, the influence of Mukhabarah contracts on business income, and on community welfare. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Mukhabarah contracts, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Mukharabah; Islamic Financial Inclusion; Library Research

Introduction

Agriculture is a field that still has potential as a source to meet people's needs in life and provide a source of income. The agricultural sector has a very large role in increasing Indonesia's economic growth because most people, especially rural communities, depend on agriculture for their livelihoods. Shareholders collaborate with land owners in various forms, namely land owners who rent out their land to shareholders, shareholders who become farmers by providing certain wages (salary), and land owners who have full rights in managing the land by the land owner. The results will be given to both parties, namely the land owner and the cultivator. Agricultural cooperation is called mukhabarah in Islamic law. One form of cooperation in the agricultural sector is an effort to synergize assets and employment opportunities so that Mukhabarah can help the community to meet their needs.

Ana L., Darwanto., (2020) in her journal stated that the Muk ha barah contract occurred in Brakas village, known as Maro. Collaboration carried out by verbal agreement with trust without witnesses and also an unknown time period. This research looks at the application of profit sharing from the perspective of a mukhabarah agreement published by the IAIN Kudus journal. The research method used is a qualitative method with qualitative descriptive. The data used in the research are primary data obtained from interviews, observations and document reviews, secondary data obtained from supporting

primary data. The aim of this research is to find out the profit sharing system used in Brakas village and the reasons for carrying out profit sharing, to find out the suitability of the maro system for mukhabarah. Suazhari (2015) discussing the implementation of the mukhabarah agreement in Panindoan Village. The data collection technique used was interviews. The approach taken is qualitative using primary data. The aim of this research is for the village community in Panindoan village to understand Islamic law and not just focus on habits or customs passed down from generation to generation which are carried out with mutual trust and verbally. Sari (2016) explains about cooperation in managing agricultural land in accordance with Islamic religious law. Because this is still a matter of debate in Islam, especially among fiqh scholars. This is aimed at whether or not there are elements of usury, gharar, maysir and others in this mukhabarah contract. This research uses Islamic sharia research methods and connects it with mukhabarah activities that occur in the surrounding community, especially in land management, agriculture and others.

of this research is to map research topics around Mukhabarah contracts using Islamic Financial Inclusion library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding the Mukhabarah contract, so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding the Mukhabarah contract, both frequently and rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

contract is managing land where the cultivator provides seeds or seedlings and then produces something from the land and the land owner provides the land to the cultivator. Mukhabarah is a form of cooperation between land owners and land cultivators with a mutual agreement. Profit sharing is important in agriculture because many people want to farm but do not have land, while there are those who own land but cannot or do not have the time to work on their land, so that with cooperation the land becomes productive and profitable. This practice is a solution for land owners and shareholders to work together and feel the benefits they get from working together.

Islamic Financial Inclusion refers to efforts to ensure that all individuals and economic entities, regardless of their economic, social, or geographic background, have fair and appropriate access to financial products and services that comply with sharia principles. Sharia principles are Islamic economic rules and guidelines that prohibit riba (interest), excessive speculation, and investment in businesses that are forbidden under Islamic law. Islamic Financial Inclusion includes a variety of financial products and services, such as savings, microfinance, insurance, investment and other financial instruments, that comply with sharia principles. The aim of Islamic Financial Inclusion is to increase public access to financial services that are in accordance with the values and principles of the Islamic religion. Islamic Financial Inclusion has a positive impact on the economy, including reducing poverty, improving community welfare, and strengthening financial system stability. Apart from that, Islamic Financial Inclusion also supports the development of the sharia financial sector as a whole, which involves financial institutions such as sharia banks, sharia insurance companies and sharia capital markets.

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of literature study research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, literature study research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and compile the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Methodology

This research uses a qualitative approach in the nature of a library research. The object of the research is the Mukhabarah contract. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about Mukhabarah agreements on Islamic Financial Inclusion. The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Mukhabarah " within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around Mukhabarah contracts based on journals that have been collected.

Results and Discussion

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Differences between Mukhabarah and Muzara'ah Agreements

library research study in previous research journals, researchers found differences between Mukhabarah and Muzara'ah contracts. The main difference between these two contracts lies in the aspects of land ownership and distribution of harvests. In the Mukhabarah agreement, the land owner owns the agricultural land and only gives part of the harvest to the farmer. Meanwhile, in the Muzara'ah contract, the land owner gives the land to the farmer to cultivate, and the harvest will be shared between the land owner and the farmer. The following are some of the differences between the two contracts:

1. Mukhabarah Agreement:
 - a. In the Mukhabarah contract, the land owner or agricultural entrepreneur (muzari') gives permission to the farmer (mukhabir) to work on his land.
 - b. In this contract, the land owner provides the land, while the farmer is responsible for providing part of the harvest to the land owner.
 - c. The share of the harvest given to the land owner is usually determined in advance in the form of a certain percentage or amount.

- d. Farmers as parties who work on the land are responsible for land management and production costs.
2. Muzara'ah Agreement:
 - a. In the Muzara'ah contract, the land owner or agricultural investor (muzara') gives land to the farmer (muzari') to cultivate.
 - b. In this contract, farmers are responsible for cultivating the land and managing the production process without providing initial costs to the land owner.
 - c. After harvest, the production will be divided between the land owner and farmers according to the previous agreement.
 - d. Profit sharing can be in the form of a certain percentage, a certain amount, or other agreement agreed to by both parties.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Implementation of Mukhabarah Agreements in the Agricultural Sector

library research study in previous research journals, researchers found the application of the Mukhabarah agreement in the agricultural sector, namely:

1. Determination of Assets: The party providing capital (muqarrij) can purchase or rent assets to be used in agricultural activities, such as land, agricultural equipment, or livestock.
2. Production Sharing Agreement: The party providing the capital and the party carrying out the agricultural business (muzara'ah) agree to share the results obtained from agricultural activities. The distribution of these results can be determined using a pre-agreed percentage or ratio.
3. Operational Financing: Muqarrij is responsible for financing agricultural operations, such as purchasing seeds, fertilizers, pesticides, land management, and other costs required in the production process.
4. Agricultural Implementation: Muzara'ah is responsible for carrying out agricultural activities in accordance with established agreements. They will work the land, care for crops, look after livestock, and carry out other necessary activities.
5. Distribution of Results: After harvest or a certain period, agricultural products will be distributed between muqarrij and muzara'ah according to a previously agreed percentage or ratio. This division of profits reflects the share that each party is entitled to based on the agreement.
6. End of Contract: After the agreement period ends, the Mukhabarah contract can be extended or terminated according to the agreement of both parties. If the contract is extended, the profit sharing can be rearranged based on new conditions and agreements.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Implementation of Mukhabarah Agreements in Salt Ponds

library research study in previous research journals, researchers found the application of the Mukhabarah agreement to salt ponds. In the Mukhabarah agreement, the salt pond owner (mukhabir) will lease his salt pond to another party (mukhabarah) to manage and produce salt. The mukhabarah will be responsible for managing the pond, including financing, maintenance and salt processing. The results of salt production will be shared between the pond owner and the mukhabarah party based on a previously determined agreement. The following are the steps for implementing the Mukhabarah agreement on salt ponds:

1. Agreement between the salt pond owner and the mukhabarah party: The parties involved must agree to the terms and conditions of the Mukhabarah agreement, including the distribution of salt production results.
2. Salt pond rental: The salt pond owner will rent out his pond to the mukhabarah party. The rental agreement must be clear regarding the rental period, rental fees, and the mukhabarah's obligations in managing the pond.
3. Pond financing and management: The mukhabarah will use the funds they have to finance the management of the salt pond. They will take care of the procurement of salt seeds, pond maintenance and salt processing.
4. Distribution of production results: After the salt harvest, the production results will be divided between the pond owner and the mukhabarah party according to the initial agreement. The distribution can be done in the form of a percentage or certain proportion.
5. Reporting and payment: The mukhabarah party must submit reports regarding the production and results of the pond periodically to the pond owner. Payment to the mukhabarah party will be made after distribution of production results according to the agreement.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Implementation of Mukhabarah Agreements in Maro Profit Sharing

Based on a review of library research studies in previous research journals, researchers found the application of the Mukhabarah agreement to Maro profit sharing, namely:

1. Capital Agreement: Muqarrib (the party providing the capital) and Maro (the party using the capital) agree on the amount of capital that the muqarrib will provide to the maro.
2. Profit Sharing: Profits generated from the business will be shared between the muqarrib and maro based on a previously determined agreement. The profit sharing can be determined in the form of a percentage or a fixed amount.
3. Liability for Losses: If the business experiences a loss, the muqarrib and maro must bear the losses according to the initial agreement. Typically, liability for losses is based on the proportion of capital paid in by each party.
4. Period and Payment: The Mukhabarah contract agreement must include the time period specified for the business. The profits obtained will be distributed according to the agreement, usually over a monthly, quarterly or annual period.
5. Ownership of Capital Goods: In a Mukhabarah contract, the muqarrib is usually the owner of the capital goods, while the maro acts as the manager or operator who uses the capital to conduct business.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Influence of Mukhabarah Agreements on Business Income

library research study in previous research journals, researchers found the effect of the Mukhabarah agreement on business income, including:

1. Access to financing: Mukhabarah contracts allow farmers to get access to financing from sharia banks. By utilizing this financing, farmers can obtain the capital necessary to increase their agricultural production. In the long term, this increase in production can increase farmers' income.

2. Risk sharing: In a Mukhabarah contract, the bank or sharia financial institution is also responsible for the assets purchased. This can help reduce the risk of losses borne by farmers in the event of crop failure or other conditions that can affect agricultural yields. In this way, farmers have protection against financial risks that could affect their income.
3. Skills improvement: Within the framework of the Mukhabarah agreement, banks or sharia financial institutions can also provide training and guidance to farmers to improve their skills in farming, agricultural management, and the use of modern agricultural technology. This improvement in skills can help farmers increase the productivity and efficiency of their agricultural businesses, which in turn can have a positive impact on their income.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Influence of Mukhabarah Agreements on Community Welfare

library research study in previous research journals, researchers found the influence of the Mukhabarah agreement on community welfare, including:

1. Access to Financing: Mukhabarah contracts can provide access to financing for people who want to own property but do not have sufficient funds to buy it in cash. With this agreement, the community can obtain financing in a way that complies with sharia principles.
2. Increased Property Ownership: Through the Mukhabarah agreement, people can own property without having to wait to save for a long period of time. This can increase the level of property ownership in society, which in turn can contribute to increased prosperity and economic stability.
3. Improved Individual Well-Being: By owning their own property, individuals can experience benefits such as housing security, residential stability, and improved overall quality of life. The presence of a Mukhabarah contract can help individuals achieve this goal and improve their welfare.
4. Economic Stimulation: The Mukhabarah Agreement can also provide a stimulus to the property sector and the economy as a whole. In the financing process, banks or financial institutions will purchase property, which in turn can encourage the growth of the property sector and stimulate related economic activities, such as construction, repairs and property trading.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 6 Mapping Research Topics using literature studies regarding Mukhabarah contracts in Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely: (1) Differences between Mukhabarah and Muzara'ah contracts; (2) Implementation of the Mukhabarah agreement in the agricultural sector; (3) Application of the Mukhabarah agreement to salt ponds; (4) Application of the Mukhabarah agreement to the profit sharing of Maro; (5) The effect of the Mukhabarah agreement on business income; and (6) The influence of the Mukhabarah agreement on community welfare.

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